

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part XI. 2-(4/6-Iodo)-thionaphthene-9'-Phenanthrene Indigos

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Manuscript received 18 April 1973; revised 25 August 1973; accepted 20 September 1973

Several dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 4-iodo and 6-iodothioindoxyl with phenanthraquinone and substituted phenanthraquinones. Their dyeing and other properties have been studied and compared with those of the isomeric 5-iodo and 7-iodo substituted dyes.

THE preparation and properties of some phenanthrene indigos with iodine at 5- and 7-position have been reported earlier^{1,2}. The present investigation deals with the preparation and properties of isomeric 4-iodo and 6-iodo dyes and also a comparative study of the absorption and molar extinction co-efficients of the 4-, 5-, 6- and 7-iodo dyes. The absorption and molar extinction co-efficient datas of the reported 7-iodo dyes have been taken.

2-(Iodo)thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene indigo

Eight dyes have been synthesised by condensing the 4-iodo or 6-iodothioindoxyl with phenanthraquinone, 2-bromophenanthraquinone, 4-nitrophenanthraquinone and 2 : 7-dinitrophenanthraquinone.

The dyes of this class are dark reddish granular crystals. They dissolve in high boiling solvents and are soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid producing characteristic colouration. Melting points of all the dyes reported are above 315°.

Substituted phenanthraquinone dyes are more easily reducible than the parent dye itself in hydro-sulphite vat at 55°-60°. Uniform and fully developed shades are not obtained on cotton although these are deeply coloured dyes. The 4'-nitro compounds, however, produce deeper shades on cotton.

The absorption maxima of the dyes have been recorded in pyridine solution on a Hilger and Watts' spectrophotometer and these together with log ϵ are shown in Table 1.

The absorption maxima and logarithm molar extinction co-efficients of the 5-iodo dyes¹ have been collated.

The absorption maxima of the dyes belonging to the 4-iodo and 5-iodo¹ series have the following sequence :

4-Iodo series :

2'-Bromo dye > unsubstituted dye > 2' : 7'-dinitro dye > 4'-nitro dye

5-Iodo series¹ :

2' : 7'-Dinitro dye > unsubstituted dye > 2'-bromo dye > 4' nitro dye

In the 6-iodo and 7-iodo series the absorption maxima of the dyes have the same order which can be arranged as :

2'-Bromo dye > 2' : 7'-dinitro dye > unsubstituted dye > 4'-nitro dye

In all the four series the 4'-nitro dyes show the lowest absorption maxima.

The logarithm molar extinction co-efficients of these dyes of the different series have the following sequence :

4-Iodo series :

2' : 7'-Dinitro dye > 2'-bromo dye > 4'-nitro dye > unsubstituted dye

5-Iodo series¹ :

2'-Bromo dye > unsubstituted dye > 4'-nitro dye > 2' : 7'-dinitro dye

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TABLE I

T = Thionaphthene		PI = Phenanthrene indigo			
Dye	Shade on cotton	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	λ_{max} in m μ	log ϵ	
M ₁ :	2-(5-Iodo) T-9'-PI ¹	Reddish Violet	Deep green	564	3.992
	2-(4-Iodo) T-9'-PI	Reddish Violet	Violet	548	3.498
	2-(7-Iodo) T-9'-PI	Reddish Violet ²	Violet ²	546.5	3.871
N ₁ :	2-(6-Iodo) T-9'-PI	Reddish Violet	Blue-violet	539	3.525
M ₂ :	2-(5-Iodo) T-9'-(2'-bromo)PI ¹	Reddish violet	Deep yellowish green	563	4.098
	2-(4-Iodo) T-9'-(2'-bromo)PI ¹	Violet	Blackish brown	552	3.804
	2-(7-Iodo) T-9'-(2'-bromo)PI	Reddish violet ²	Deep yellowish green ²	550.5	3.631
N ₂ :	2-(6-Iodo) T-9'-(2'-bromo)PI	Violet	Deep brown	550	3.807
M ₃ :	2-(5-Iodo) T-9'-(4'-nitro)PI ¹	Bluish violet	Deep yellowish green	556	3.858
	2-(4-Iodo) T-9'-(4'-nitro)PI	Chocolate	Dark brown	540	3.711
	2-(7-Iodo) T-9'-(4'-nitro)PI	Bluish violet ²	Deep yellowish green ²	523	3.804
N ₃ :	2-(6-Iodo) T-9'-(4'-nitro)PI	Reddish violet	Deep violet	522	3.788
M ₄ :	2-(5-Iodo) T-9'-(2' : 7'-dinitro)PI ¹	Brownish chocolate	Green	567	3.799
	2-(4-Iodo) T-9'-(2' : 7'-dinitro)PI	Dark chocolate	Dark violet	547.5	3.865
	2-(7-Iodo) T-9'-(2' : 7'-dinitro)PI	Brownish chocolate ²	Deep green ²	547	3.440
N ₄ :	2-(6-Iodo) T-9'-(2' : 7'-dinitro)PI	Chocolate	Reddish violet	543	3.505

6-Iodo series :

2'-Bromo dye > 4'-nitro dye > unsubstituted dye > 2' : 7'-dinitro dye

7-Iodo series :

Unsubstituted dye > 4'-nitro dye > 2'-bromo dye > 2' : 7'-dinitro dye

Among the arene thioindigos the phenanthraquinone dye absorb at the longest wavelength, the values of which are comparable with those of the symmetrical thioindigos³. The three aromatic π sextets of the phenanthrene system extend the area of the electron cloud leading to enhanced absorption maxima.

The absorption maxima for the different iodo derivatives of 2-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene indigos synthesised have been given in Table I. The order of the absorption maxima for the various dyes with iodo substituent at different positions is $5 > 4 > 7 > 6$ and this order is the same as that found for the thioindigos and the hemithioindirubines studied³. As expected a single mono substituent on the arene portion of these indigo dyes produces only a slight change in the absorption maxima. Moreover, a nitro substituent at the meta position to the carbon linked to the thionaphthene ring produces a hypsochromic effect on the absorption maxima. A nitro group on the phenanthrene ring depletes the arene ring to some extent of its electronic charge so that less is available for spreading over the whole dye molecule and this is probably most

TABLE 2

Dyes	Reactants	Yield %	Formula	Analysis	
				% Found	%Reqd.
M ₁	Ph(0.39 g.)+M(0.518 g.)+AcOH(25 ml.)	44.6	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ SI	I : 27.31 S : 6.75	27.25 6.86
M ₂	2-Bromo Ph(0.377 g.)+M(0.362 g.)+AcOH(20 ml.)	62.9	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ BrSI Br+I	I : 38.15	37.98
M ₃	4-Nitro Ph(0.379 g.)+M(0.414 g.)+AcOH(ml.)	49.4	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ NSI	I : 24.72	24.85
M ₄	2 : 7-Dinitro Ph(0.47 g.)+M(0.448 g.)+AcOH(80 ml.)	41	C ₂₂ H ₉ O ₆ N ₂ SI	I : 22.76	22.84
N ₁	Ph(0.39 g.)+N(0.518 g.)+AcOH(30 ml.)	44.6	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ SI	I : 27.31 S : 6.75	27.25 6.86
N ₂	2-Bromo Ph(0.503 g.)+N(0.483 g.)+AcOH(30 ml.)	52.4	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ BrSI Br+I	I : 37.85	37.98
N ₃	4-Nitro Ph(0.379 g.)+N(0.414 g.)+AcOH(20 ml.)	70.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ NSI	I : 24.97	24.85
N ₄	2 : 7-Dinitro Ph(0.47 g.)+N(0.448 g.)+AcOH(80 ml.)	35.4	C ₂₂ H ₉ O ₆ N ₂ SI	I : 22.92	22.84

pronounced when the negative substituent is at the meta position to the carbon linking the arene to the thionaphthene portion of the dye molecule.

Experimental

The general method for the preparation of these dyes has been the condensation of the reactants in equimolecular proportion in boiling glacial acetic acid in presence of a small amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid. They were boiled with ethanol to remove the unreacted products and crystallised from xylene.

For the sake of brevity, the proportion of the reactants, yields, m.p. etc. of the prepared dyes are given in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

Authors' thanks are due to Dr. Amitava Ghosh, Bose Institute, Calcutta for his help with spectrophotometer and to Dr. J. C. Banerji, Head of the Department of Chemistry, B. N. College, Patna for laboratory facilities and encouragement.

References

1. A. K. SINHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 478.
2. S. K. PODDAR, A. K. SINHA and J. C. BANERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 654.
3. A. K. DAS and A. K. SINHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, under publication.